

UNIQUE INTERPRETATION OF HOMONYMS AND POLYSEMY PHENOMENA IN TERMINOLOGY

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Abstract. *Polysemy and a similar lexical phenomenon - homonymy are one of the topics that have attracted the attention of researchers and linguists as important parts of lexicology. This article discusses the specific characteristics, similarities and differences of the phenomena of homonymy and polysemy, as well as the issue of their use in field terminology.*

Keywords: *homonymy, polysemy, ambiguity, transfer of meaning, terminologists.*

As long as any language exists in society, it always develops, adapts to society according to the needs of the time, and incorporates changes and updates in it. This, of course, depends on the language skills of the speakers of that language. Changes and updates in the language affect the speech of individuals and are felt in the speech of a person depending on different situations and circumstances. As the position of a certain language in social life is disappearing, along with this language, the cultural wealth of the language's owners, national identities, and most importantly, the lexical units that express the subtle meanings unique to this language, are also disappearing. There are several reasons for such consequences. In particular, the decrease of the number of speakers of this language, the dominance of developed languages over the language, the lack of development of a mechanism for scientific research and development of a particular language, and the decrease of its value in the life of society are modern factors that cause languages to become dead languages. The language under attention and protection continues to develop and rise depending on the development of society.

In linguistics, we can observe many scientific studies within the framework of the study of the phenomenon of homonymy and polysemy. Among them, I.S. Tishler, J. Jileron, A.I. Smirnisky, A.A. Potebnya, L.A. Bulakhovsky, V.V. Vinogradov, I.V. Arnold, R.A. Budagov, V.V. Brown, O.M. Zhilyaeva, O.S. Akhmanova, A.A. Reformatsky, N.A. Abdurakhmanov, M. Mirtojyev, I. Ko' Chkhortoyev, A. Hojiyev, etc., have carried out important scientific research on this topic.

In addition, in the 60s and 80s of the 20th century, I. Arnold (studied lexical and grammatical categories of English nouns and the semantic structure of polysemous nouns), O. Akhmanova (compiled a dictionary of homonyms), Yu. Apresyan (the structure of the semantic field was studied), A. Budagov (the interval between polysemy and homonymy was determined), V. Vinogradov (the types of lexical meaning were determined), F. Dreyzina (the syntactic analysis of polysemy was conducted). The analysis of theoretical works in the scientific works of scientists such as A. Smirnisky (the lexical and grammatical ratio of the word is determined) shows that the theoretical analysis of the problem of distinguishing polysemy and homonymy has been carried out. We can see the proof of these works in the following.

Dividing words into homonyms, synonyms, antonyms, and paronyms according to the relationship of form and meaning in the language helps to distinguish the subtle meaning of lexemes and the beautiful and impressive expression of speech. Homonyms with the same form

and different meanings are words that have a special place in terms of form and style of use. We should also mention that there are different reasons and factors for the occurrence of homonyms:

- the forms of some words that have existed in the language since long ago become equal by chance.

- a word with one meaning becomes a word with multiple meanings as a result of the transfer of the lexical meaning, later the connection between the main meaning and the derived meaning is forgotten and based on one word two different lexemes appear;

- some lexemes acquired from other languages, mainly Persian, remain formally equivalent to one or another lexeme in the Uzbek language;

- the meeting of words with the same form among lexemes borrowed from other languages leads to homonymy;

- the formation of lexemes also sometimes gives rise to homonyms.

And polysemy is the fact that language units have more than one meaning. Polysemy is a multifaceted and complex phenomenon. The development of the lexical meaning of almost every word requires a clear, individual approach and interpretation. Ambiguous meaning is known only in the text. For example, my mother's eyes still see well (member); eye of a spring, eye of a needle (hole); the eye of the ring (the stone set in the ring); eye of the board (circular shape on the board).

Ambiguity occurs in two ways:

- 1) as a result of acquiring a new meaning of the word.

- 2) as a result of forming a word from a polysemous word or by means of a polysemous adverb.

Synonymy, homonymy, and polysemy are the wealth of the language in the literary language, but in terminology, these are negative phenomena. For this reason, in all languages with somewhat stable terminology, terms are constantly regulated. Some linguists consider all separate meanings of polysemantic words to be homonyms. In this case, there is a view that polysemy is a special type and state of homonymy.

But despite this, cases of homonymy and polysemy are observed in the terminology. Interdisciplinary terminological homonymy was noted by A.A.Reformatsky as a special type of formalism. Its essence is that one term can belong to different terminological systems of a particular language, and it constitutes interdisciplinary terminological homonymy.

The study of linguistic and non-linguistic phenomena, thereby enriching and expanding professional languages, provides a wide opportunity to establish new trends and the formation of terminological units. It should be noted that in the field of linguistics, research on the problem of determining the structural differences between polysemy and homonymy has been carried out for many years. Scientists have different opinions on this matter, because researchers interpret the polysemy of lexical units from different points of view.

Based on the comparative analysis of the scientific sources devoted to the terminology of the following years, the following should be noted:

- a) terminological homonymy has been the subject of a small amount of research compared to synonymy and polysemy;

- b) terminological homonymy is often studied in comparison with polysemy;

- c) most of the studies are based on the terminology of one field.

Also, S. V. Grinev pays special attention to the development of criteria for distinguishing homonymy and polysemy in terminology. As the researcher noted, "cases in which several concepts are expressed by one lexical unit can be qualified as polysemy and homonymy".

A similar analog view is O.S. It is also based on Akhmanova's scientific works. It clearly expresses the concept of distinguishing between polysemy and homonymy in terminology. According to Unig, "if two terms are identical in terms of expression, but different in content, this phenomenon looks like polysemy in one terminological system and homonymy in different terminology. Because homonymy of terms occurs mainly through semantic migration. In the formation of new terms using the metonymic process, both terms - the old and the new term derived from it - are often not separated by their use in different terminological systems, but remain in the same language, and the connection between them can be very clearly observed.

From the above points, we can conclude that although the boundary between homonymy and polysemy in terminology is unclear in most cases, we must not forget that there is a clear context that studies the characteristics of these concepts, the study of the differences of lexical units, and the criteria for determining the true value of this polysemic term. The migration of word meanings, as well as the widening and narrowing of meaning in words, phenomena such as homonymy and polysemy in words are important because they are different aspects of lexical meaning. The development of the meaning of the form in words is a continuous process, which from time to time realizes various linguistic phenomena. The lexical meaning of a word plays a decisive role in distinguishing it from other types of lexical meaning. The emergence of words with new meanings in Uzbek terminology is a phenomenon related to this lexical meaning.

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